



Fig SF4.1 - 4 : Complement to Fig 2 C ii - v, FigSF4.4: All are significant except CA1 vs. PA3



Fig SF4.5 : Complement to Fig 4C



Fig SF4.6 - 11: Complement to Fig 5E



Fig SF4.12 and 13: Normalized systolic and active stress by Average Sarcomere density